

MEDICAL SCIENCES

SERUM FERRITIN LEVELS IN CHILDREN WITH B-THALASSEMIA

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Abstract

In the study, changes in iron and ferritin concentrations in the blood serum of β -thalassemia patients receiving desferal therapy were studied. 125 One patient with β -thalassemia was examined. 68 of them were boys and 53 were girls. The control group consisted of 20 healthy people. Depending on the clinical course of the disease, the examined patients were treated with desferal in different doses. After taking Desferal, the concentration of ferritin in the blood of patients was determined. Thus, the decrease in the concentration of ferritin depends on the dose of Desferal. Thus, the use of desferal therapy in the treatment of β -thalassemia patients has been shown to be appropriate. The determination of ferritin in the blood serum can play an important role in maintaining the normal level of liver and spleen function in this group of diseases, allowing for accurate selection of desferal dose dynamically.

Keywords: ferritin, desferal, β -thalassemia

The accumulation of excess iron in organs and tissues is one of the main reasons for the development of complications in diseases requiring regular replacement transfusions of erythrocyte mass [1]. These diseases include β -thalassemia. β -Thalassemia is caused by a defect in the synthesis of only the β -chain, it is divided into β^+ thalassemia, in which the synthesis of the β -chain is preserved, and β^0 -thalassemia synthesis of the β -chain is completely absent. β^0 - and β^+ - thalassemia are characterized by the accumulation of iron in various organs [2]. The human body is well adapted to the accumulation of iron from the outside in iron deficiency states, or in anemia, as well as to a decrease in the utilization of iron from the macrophage system during inflammation [3].

To eliminate excess iron introduced into the body with transfused blood uses iron-removing compounds, that is, drugs that are able to bind iron and remove it from the body. The main medical iron chelator drug available to physicians is currently time is desferal (desferrioxamine) [4]. The optimal dose of Desferal can be calculated by determining the total amount of iron and ferritin received by the patient (iron received in the body as part of the transfused blood, plus absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract) and the amount of metal excreted from the body as a result of the use of various doses of Desferal [5].

Materials and research methods. 125 patients (68 boys and 53 girls) with β -thalassemia major were under observation. The control group consisted of 20 healthy individuals. The diagnosis was made on the basis of the determination of the hemoglobin fractions HbA2 and HbF using the isoelectric focusing method on polyacryl-ampholine plastics with a pH of 3.5-9.5 using a Multiphor 2117 instrument from LKB (Sweden). The amount of ferritin was determined by enzyme immunoassay using a Stat Fax apparatus (USA).

Results. In patients with β -thalassemia, the amount of Hb is 3.4 times, erythrocytes - 1.76 times, hematocrit 1.5 times less than in healthy. Hemoglobin fractions in patients with β -thalassemia showed an increased level of HbF, it was found to be $60.5 \pm 2.1\%$,

which is 42.6 times higher than in healthy individuals. The amounts of HbA2 in both groups were similar; in patients $1.42 \pm 0.08\%$ (norm $2.07 \pm 0.14\%$). When studying iron metabolism in patients with β -thalassemia, an increased content of serum iron and ferritin was revealed. The level of serum iron in patients with β -thalassemia was increased 1.6 times, 33.7 ± 2.5 , serum ferritin was 2254.6 ± 186.3 31 times compared with the control group.

Before taking desferal, the average level of ferritin in patients was 3574.0 ± 441.4 units, and in 75% of cases, ferritin the limit of 2020.0 units prevailed, and in 25% of cases - 4265.0 units, in some cases taking values close to 10000 units, even in one patient reaching the level of 14140 ng/l. After the first intake of Desferal, the average level of ferritin in the blood decreased to an average of 2734.3 ± 358.3 ng/l. These changes were statistically insignificant ($p_U = 0.079$), since in half of the cases the ferritin level remained above the limit of 2318.0 ng/l, and in 25% of cases it was higher than 3260.0 units. But at the same time, in all 35 patients, a decrease in the ferritin index in the blood was observed ($p_W < 0.001$)

29 patients took desferal for the 2nd time, because in 6 patients the ferritin level after the first dose dropped to the reference values. After the 2nd dose of Desferal, the average level of ferritin in the blood was 2452.3 ± 373.7 units. at the same time, in half of the cases, the ferritin level did not exceed the limit of 2000.0 units. and in 25% of cases were less than 1119.0 units, while a quarter of the patients had rather high rates - more than 3076.0 units, in no patient the ferritin level did not exceed 9450 units. There was a significant difference from baseline ($p_{OU} = 0.014$), which cannot be asserted from the level of the previous Desferal session ($p_U = 0.294$). A more detailed statistical analysis revealed a decrease in ferritin in all patients compared with the previous treatment session. ($p_W < 0.001$). In further treatment sessions, the same picture was observed: the ferritin level decreased on average from 2512.5 ± 411.5 ng/l up to 1136.5 ± 1958.8 ng/l

Conclusions. With the help of the regression model, we can predict the process in further treatment sessions with 95% probability level. Thus, the results of the conducted laboratory studies indicate the expediency of using desferal therapy in the complex treatment of β -thalassemia major as effective. Intermediate link in treatment. Determining the level of ferritin after each dose of Desferal is the main indicator of iron stores in examined patients with β -thalassemia major.

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ESOPHAGEAL ADENOCARCINOMA: GENERAL INFORMATION

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Abstract

The publication provides detailed information on the classification, epidemiology, etiology and pathogenesis of esophageal adenocarcinoma.

Аннотация

В статье выполнен подробный обзор литературы, содержащей сведения о научных взглядах на классификацию, эпидемиологию, этиологию и патогенез аденокарциномы пищевода.

Keywords: adenocarcinoma of the esophagus, esophageal adenocarcinoma, tumors of the esophageal-gastric junction, etiology and pathogenesis of malignant neoplasms of the esophagus.

Ключевые слова: аденокарцинома пищевода, опухоли пищеводно-желудочного перехода, этиология и патогенез злокачественных новообразований пищевода.

Определение и классификация. Аденокарцинома пищевода (АП) – злокачественное новообразование (ЗНО), отличающееся крайне неблагоприятным прогнозом, что принято связывать с поздним выявлением, обычно, после достижения запущенных стадий. Эта особенность АП привела к тому, что в последнее время ведется большое количество исследований по изучению механизмов ее развития, а также заставило многих специалистов принять тезис о необходимости тщательного агрессивного наблюдения за пациентами с ПБ и ГЭРБ [8-12].

Классификация аденокарцином кардиоэзофагеальной области, включающих в себя в том числе и АП, предложена J.R. Siewert и A.H. Holscher в 1996 году [13]. Она основана на 2 параметрах: гистологическом строении опухоли (аденокарцино-

нома) и локализации ее анатомического центра относительно пищеводно-желудочного перехода (ПЖП). Эта система рекомендована согласительной конференцией Международной ассоциации по раку желудка и Международного общества по заболеваниям пищевода и характеризуется простотой и высокой воспроизводимостью.

Классификация Зиверта разделяет аденокарциномы ПЖП на 3 типа (рис. 1):

- I тип: аденокарцинома дистального отдела пищевода, с расположением центра в пределах от 1 до 5 см выше ПЖП (Z-линии) с возможностью распространения через последнюю в сторону желудка (собственно АП);

- II тип: истинная аденокарцинома ПЖП (истинный рак кардии), центр опухоли расположен в пределах от 1 см проксимально до 2 см дистально ПЖП (Z-линии);